

Teaching English As A Second Language Among Business Students: An Investigation Of Intention Towards Online Learning During The Different Waves Of Covid-19

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 02, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 04, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : English, Business Students, Intention Towards Online Learning, Waves Of Covid-19, Developing Country</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5160215</p>	<p><i>In the present era, knowing the students' intention towards online learning is become necessary due to the persisting situations of the COVID-19. The current paper explores the teaching of English as a second language among business students through intention towards online learning due to different waves of COVID-19 in Pakistan. The research is conceptualized based on literature. The study used a deductive method that utilizes cross-sectional data. The study employed a random sampling technique to trace the respondents. By using the AMOS, the results of a study underline a positive significant effect of performance expectancy (PE), effort expectancy (EE), social influence (SI), facilitating conditions (FC) and perceived usefulness (PU) on intention towards online learning (ITOL) among the business students. The study's findings would assist policymakers and planners in knowing further about the individuals' intention towards online learning during the different pandemics. The study would also provide valuable insights to comprehend the elements that influence online learning (OL) concerning the teaching of English, who's English is a second language. In the last, results of a study would contribute to the arts, management and psychology's literature to further recognize the intention, English teaching and its connections, particularly in a miserable condition of COVID-19 in a developing country.</i></p>

Introduction

In the present era, advanced technology has brought education online through technological advancement. Such a scenario predominantly came through the outbreak of COVID-19 (Shah et al., 2020). Online education system appears to be effective and crucial, particularly for higher education, as most colleges and universities are engaged to conduct their education (Yunus et al., 2021; Soomro & Shah, 2021a). However, in tertiary education, it has been become a severe issue due to unavailability of the digital technological access (Kopp et al., 2019; Yunus et al., 2021). The system has functioned with diverse online learning and teaching tools. For instance, some institutes use massive open online courses, social media, virtual learning environments, mobile applications, and others to apply educational web services. In various cases, online learning is a prerequisite of the day due to the pandemic. In 2020, all sectors and segments of the economy had been seriously affected by the COVID-19. Among this education sector was the robust victim. Almost every country decided and declared to their citizens to stay at home and inspire social distancing to stop the spreading of the pandemic.

With regard to students, they are trying to convert their approaches from physical education to digital learning (Mulenga & Marbán, 2020). BI of the learners regarding online learning remains the central issue in the education sector. Several studies have examined the students' acuties on learning English through technological usage during non-pandemic situations (Zinan & Sai, 2017; Sharma, 2019). On the other hand, there is a lack of empirical evidence of examination of intention towards online learning that may be conducted during the different waves of the pandemic in Pakistan. Due to the pandemic, all higher education institutes are seriously affected and closed for the different waves (Lakhan et al., 2021a; Soomro et al., 2021). Students of the various institutes tried to continue their education online (Soomro & Abdelwahed, 2021). Henceforth, it is necessary to inspect the students ITOL among the business students of the diverse universities of Pakistan by focusing teaching English as the second language that is most significant for the students' daily lives (Shahzad et al., 2020).

The present study proposes the investigation of ITOL during the different waves of COVID-19. The findings of a survey would provide significant insights into the higher education contexts. The study would further offer the effectiveness of the online learning (OL) and be fruitful to the academic leadership and policymakers to consider the business students' perceptions of OL. It would increase awareness concerning the constructs and obstacles that impact students' behavioural intention (BI) to use OL.

Literature review and hypotheses development

The outbreak of COVID-19 has significantly transferred the physical education system into an online learning system. Such an e-learning system depends upon the technology. In this regard, the finding of the study of Qiao et al. (2021) highlights the focus of e-learning on the infrastructure to reach more users after the outbreak of COVID-19. It is due to e-learning is the only significant source of acquiring education. Fear is a potent factor that moderated the association between the external predictors and the BI of e-learning users. The adaptation of new technology can be affected and weakened by a lack of financial support. Social Isolation provides more occasions for students to involve in e-learning. In the meantime, it breaks down the operation of e-learning since of out-to-date software and hardware. Zawaideh (2017) posits the importance of the e-learning environment of a university's infrastructural features in a similar domain. The findings of a study demonstrate a significant and positive association of PE, EE, SI and FC with BI to use e-learning. In Turkey and United Kingdom, Kurt and Tingöy (2017) conducted a study among undergraduate students. The scholars tested the significance of PE, EE, FC and SI in both contexts. The outcomes of a survey confirmed BI and user behaviour concerning the use of OL environment in HEC changed between the two nations. Besides, an effectiveness of constructs from use behaviour and BI also varied from one construct to another. Soomro et al. (2020) indicates that intention can be predicted through perceived feasibility and desirability. The TPB theory is robust in developing the technopreneurship intention (Soomro & Shah, 2021b). Similarly, Memon et al. (2019) demonstrate the predictor power of self-efficacy in developing entrepreneurship intention. According to Stephenson (2018), there is a growing trend of technology and the internet, which significantly transferred the traditional classroom to online learning (OL). The OL includes online learning and teaching, which occupy the learners' learning process through digital media and the internet. It shapes mobile learning through mobile computational maneuvers and electronic devices (Almutairi et al., 2017). In the perception of Selwyn (2003), technology-based learning is an innovative learning method that is better for primary and secondary schools. Nevertheless, it is more effective in higher-level education. The usage of ICT in education is helpful to teachers to do managerial responsibilities more capably and students to learn more competently. Internet access malformed education, signaling a new era where technology arbitrated gears were recycled to supernumerary the traditional teaching with a learning procedure denoted as online learning (Yakubu et al., 2018). Similarly, Devisakti and Ramayah (2019) supported OL as an alternative approach to conventional face-to-face teaching and learning. It develops the interaction between students and teachers effectively. The applications, i.e. Google Meet and ZOOM, allow the lesson to be brought live, where the students could interrelate with each other in real-time (Basilaia & Kvavadze, 2020). Google Classroom is one of the online learning podiums that assists teachers to increase interpersonal communication among students and save time (Iftakhar, 2017). In the prevailing situation of the COVID-19 pandemic, it is necessary to limit such a dangerous spread globally (UNICEF, 2021). The institutes such as schools, colleges and universities have rapidly been closed. The establishments can change to replacement which is online learning programs (Clancy & Sentance, 2020). Consequently, the domain literature provided different assumptions regarding online learning. We projected the following model (figure 1) to assess ITOL among business students in a developing country based on such factors.

Figure 1. Model of the study

PE is an extent to which individuals undertake OL would increase their learning procedure (Yunus et al., 2021). Venkatesh et al. (2003) reveals that the PE is associated with trust of individuals that using ICT would assist in enhancing the success of their mission. It develops the PU, extrinsic motivation and comparative benefit, which increases expectancies of online learning usage. In the perception of Taiwo and Downe (2013) and Ngampornchai and Adams (2016), PE is the significant predictor of BI of the students. Zawaideh (2017) conducted a study and found PE's association with behavioural intention to use e-learning. Similarly, Handoko (2019) supported the positive relationship between PE and BI. Besides, among the postgraduate students of public university of Malaysia, the empirical study of Yunus et al. (2021) highlights a significant and positive impact of PE on ITOL in pandemic situations. EE is regarded as the ease of using a specific system. EE significantly and positively affects the BI to use e-learning in the Malaysian context (Zawaideh, 2017). The same findings are strongly supported by Handoko (2019) and claim EE's positive and significant effect on BI. Likewise, SI has considerable importance, which is usually associated with an individual accord to the thoughts of others concerning their use of a new system. According to Handoko (2019), SI is a robust analyst of BI. It has a significant and positive correlation with BI (Zawaideh, 2017). Along with these factors, FC is valuable for usage and connected with the individual's belief in the essential technical and organizational infrastructure (Kurt & Tingöy, 2017). A quantitative study was conducted by Handoko (2019) from 365 students of the online learning program. The outcomes of a study highlight that the factors such as PE, EE, personal innovativeness and quality of service significantly affect the BI. Further, BI impacts use behaviour, whereas FC does not affect user behaviour. Similarly, in Egypt, PE, learners' autonomy, FC, and SI positively associate with BI to use m-learning. In contrast, EE has appeared with no impact on intention to use mobile learning (Ali & Arshad, 2018). By employing the UTAUT constructs, the findings of Alshehri et al. (2020) confirm the UTAUT parameters as robust and valid and robust in the context of LMS in Saudi Arabia in colleges and universities. Besides, the aspect of SI arisen to affect the students' usage behaviour and intention significantly. The PE is influenced by system interactivity and information quality. On the other hand, the EE was affected by instructional assessment, system learnability and system navigation.

Consequently, the relevant literature emphasizes the significant effect of PE, EE, SI, FC and PU on ITOL (Venkatesh et al., 2003; Kaba & Touré, 2014; Hou, 2014; Diño & de Guzman, 2015) in the different contexts. However, a limited number of studies are found in the Pakistani context particularly in business students in English as a second language (Taiwo & Downe, 2013; Ngampornchai & Adams, 2016; Zawaideh, 2017; Handoko, 2019; Yunus et al., 2021). On the basis of unavailability of valuable investigation, we suggest:

- H1. PE positively and significantly predicts ITOL.
- H2. EE positively and significantly predicts ITOL.
- H3. SI positively and significantly predicts ITOL.
- H4. FC positively and significantly predicts ITOL.

H5. PU positively and significantly predicts ITOL.

Methods

We employed a deductive approach based on a quantitative manner. We correctly followed the previous domain scholars like Kurt and Tingöy (2017), Ali and Arshad (2018), Alshehri et al. (2020), Qiao et al. (2021) and Yunus et al. (2021). They already conducted such types of studies in various contexts. The base of investigation is on cross-sectional data. The cross-sectional data is valuable due to saving time and cost (Soomro et al., 2019; Lakhani et al., 2021b).

A random technique is employed to trace the respondents of the study. The study participants are business individuals of the several general universities of Pakistan that mainly offer business degrees with English as a second language. We visited the contexts of the study, where we followed proper governmental SOPs. However, we attained a few data through emails and doc services due to movement restrictions of the COVID-19. Before handing over the questionnaires to the respondents, we got their consent to participate in the study. They were made aware of the study's aim and purposes. We properly got them to ensure the usage of their data and the confidentiality of their personal information.

We collected 222 valid samples and utilized them for final analysis. We employed AMOS version 26.0 for the examination of the data.

Data analysis and results

In total, 222 students of business have participated in the study. The demographic trend underlines a majority of male students (68.47% or n=152) as compared to female students (31% or n=70) (Table 1). We found many students (76% or n=170) between 20-25 years of age. The less than 20 years were found as 21% or 47 students. On the other hand, a low ratio of age among 26-30 was observed with only 0.1%. Finally, only one student was seen above 31 years (Table 1).

Table 1. Demography

	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	152	68.47
	Female	70	31.53
	Total	222	100.0
Age (years)	<20	47	21.17
	20-25	170	76.58
	26-30	04	01.80
	31 and >	01	00.45
	Total	222	100.0

We examined the descriptive statistics to perceive the demographic trend of participants. We noticed the upper range of mean (3.888) for the ITOL construct, and a lower range of mean was observed (3.032) for SI (Table 2). Likewise, the standard deviation score suggests a maximum score (1.254) for SI, while minimum ranges of the score were observed (0.002) for the EE predictor. Besides, we confirmed the correlation among the constructs through Pearson's correlation (r) coefficients. As a result, all the factors have appeared with satisfactory correlation scores in ranges, and there is no assumption of multicollinearity (Table 2).

Before going to assess the hypotheses, the model fitness was ensured. The values for such indicators, i.e. the CMIN= χ^2 /chi-square, occurred to be 2.456 (Table 3). Similarly, other model's fit indices, i.e. GFI=0.928, AGFI=0.932, NFI=0.919, CFI=0.906, and RMSEA=0.031 are appeared within the suitable values (Table 3 and Figure 2).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics, and correlation matrix

Variables	Mean	Std. deviation	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. ITOL	3.888	0.975	---					
2. PE	3.223	0.890	0.333**	---				
3. EE	3.768	1.002	0.419**	0.291*	---			
4. SI	3.032	1.254	0.393**	0.473**	0.149*	---		

5. FC	3.098	1.200	0.325**	0.432**	0.239*	0.223*	---
6. PU	3.283	0.805	0.398**	0.328**	0.346**	0.349**	0.459**

**,*Correlations are significant at 0.01 and 0.05 levels, respectively (two-tailed)

Table 3. Model fitness

Model fit indicators	CMIN/df	GFI	AGFI	NFI	CFI	RMSEA
	2.456	0.928	0.932	0.919	0.906	0.031
Recommended values	< 3	> 0.90	> 0.90	> 0.90	> 0.90	<0.05

Note: CMIN= χ^2 /Chi-square/df; df= degree of freedom; GFI=goodness of fit index; AGFI=adjusted goodness of fit index; NFI= normed fit index; CFI= comparative fit index; RMSEA=root mean square error of approximation

We applied the path analysis through AMOS to confirm the proposed hypotheses. The results suggest a substantial impact of PE on ITOL (SE=0.044, CR=5.330***; p<0.01) (figure 2 and Table 4). Therefore, H1 is supported. The proposed path between EE and ITOL is supported (SE=0.068; CR=6.078***; p<0.01). Henceforth, H2 is supported. Likewise, the analysis also confirmed the considerable influence of SI on ITOL (SE=0.059, CR=6.563***; p<0.01), which accepted H3. With regard to H4, the SE, CR and p values (SE=0.064, CR=5.776***; p<0.01) are appeared to be in favour of acceptance of H4. Finally, PU has seemed as the substantial analyst of ITOL (SE=0.078, CR=4.372***; p<0.01) (figure 2 and Table 4).

Table 4. Path analysis

H.No.	IVs	Path	DV	Estimate	SE	CR	P	Decision
H1	PE	→	ITOL	0.244	0.044	5.330	***	Accepted
H2	EE	→	ITOL	0.254	0.068	6.078	***	Accepted
H3	SI	→	ITOL	0.338	0.059	6.563	***	Accepted
H4	FC	→	ITOL	0.403	0.064	5.776	***	Accepted
H5	PU	→	ITOL	0.398	0.078	4.372	***	Accepted

Note: SE=standard error; CR=critical ratio; p=significance level ***p<0.05
IVs=independent variables; DV=dependent variable

Figure 2. Path analysis

Note:
SE=standard error;
CR=critical ratio;
p=significance level
***p<0.05

PE=performance expectancy; EE=effort expectancy; SI=Social influence; FC=facilitating conditions; PU=perceived usefulness; ITOL=intention towards online learning

Discussion and Conclusion

The research investigated ITOL among business students whose teaching English as a second language. We investigated such problems during the different waves of the COVID-19 pandemic. We employed quantitative methods, which is based on 222 valid samples. These samples were collected through a random sampling technique. A questionnaire was used as a principal instrument for the data gathering. Through the AMOS, outcomes of a study underline a substantial constructive effect of PE on ITOL, which accepted the H1. Such the results are unailing with the earlier findings like Taiwo and Downe (2013), Ngampornchai and Adams (2016), Zawaideh (2017), Handoko (2019) and Yunus et al. (2021), who provided the same outcomes earlier. The present findings suggest that OL significantly increases the individuals' intention to adopt the OL during the pandemic. Likewise, the second hypothesis was accepted by the data, which confirmed the positive association between EE and ITOL (H2 supported). These results are in line with several scholars, i.e. Zawaideh (2017), Ali and Arshad (2018), Handoko (2019), and Alshehri et al. (2020), who claimed the significant and positive linkages between EE and ITOL in the different contexts. The present study's findings may reflect that personal innovativeness and quality of service significantly affect the BI.

Similarly, the path analysis supported the positive relationship between SI and ITOL. These results accepted the H3. Similar to other studies, the present findings are supported by several studies (Zawaideh, 2017; Kurt & Tingöy, 2017; Handoko, 2019). The study underlines that the SI has the powerful influence that diverted the students to adopt OL. Further, the findings showed a significant linkage between FC and ITOL (H4 supported). In the literature, these associations existed earlier, i.e. Zawaideh (2017), Kurt and Tingöy (2017) and Handoko (2019), who demonstrated similar correlations. FC was found as a strong belief in individuals' towards essential technical and organizational infrastructure in the study. Finally, the path analysis found the significant relationship of PU with ITOL, which supported the H5. The findings are in line with the outcomes of Ngampornchai and Adams (2016), Zawaideh (2017), Handoko (2019) and Yunus et al. (2021), who pointed the positive associations. These findings highlighted that the PU play a vital role in developing the business students ITOL among the different universities of Pakistan.

In conclusion, the inclusive results underline a significant and positive effect of PE, EE, SI, FC and PU on ITOL among the business students who learn English as a second language. The findings of an investigation would deliver the strategies to developers and policymakers to design the procedures and strategies that further create the interest and intention to learn through OL. Lastly, the study's outcomes may contribute and deepen the depth of the literature of arts, management and COVID-19 situations.

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